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THE DISCRIMINATION OF EUDR ON PALM OIL POTENTIALLY VIOLATES WTO PRINCIPLES

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RESUME

The EUDR policy prohibits palm oil linked to deforestation from entering the European Union market. The implementation of this policy is a form of discriminatory treatment and has the potential to violate the WTO non-discrimination principles. The principles referred to include: (1) the principle of non-discrimination in trade between countries (Most Favored Nation/MFN); (2) the principle of non-discrimination of imported like goods compared to domestic production (National Treatment/NT); (3) non-tariff barriers in trade; and (4) the discriminatory Technical Barrier to Trade (TBT) principle.

INTRODUCTION

After the discriminatory policy on palm biodiesel in the 2018 RED II Delegated Regulation ([PASPI Monitor, 2019](#)), the European Union has once again launched an anti-deforestation policy that is discriminatory against palm oil. The European Union prohibits palm oil and its derivative products into the European Union because it is deemed associated with the conversion of forests into non-forests (deforestation).

In general, the European Union Deforestation-free Regulation On Supply Chain (EUDR) policy prohibits palm oil linked to deforestation from entering the European Union market ([PASPI Monitor, 2022, 2023^a](#)). To ascertain whether palm oil is linked to deforestation, a traceability on supply chain is conducted using the methodology set (and implemented) by the EU. Thus, operators are required to submit geolocation data which will then be subjected to due diligence related to risk assessment and risk mitigation, and then certification will be carried out, where the entire process is controlled by the EU ([PASPI Monitor, 2023^d](#)).

In the context of global vegetable oils, EUDR only applies to imported palm oil and soybean oil. Meanwhile, for other vegetable oils, whether imported or produced within the EU, the EUDR policy does not apply. This shows that the EUDR policy has the potential to violate the trade principles established by the World Trade Organization (WTO). The principle in question is related to the principle of non-discrimination, where there are differences in treatment of like goods both from domestic production and from imports.

This article will discuss EUDR policy arguments that discriminate against palm oil. This will then be followed by a discussion on how EUDR has the potential to violate WTO global trade principles.

EUDR POLICY

The European Union Deforestation-free Regulation on Supply Chain (EUDR) policy is outlined in Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 2023 on the making available on the Union market and the export from the Union of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation and repealing Regulation (EU) no. 995/2010.

The EUDR policy was published in the EU Official Journal on 9 June 2023 and was implemented as a binding rule as of 29 June 2023 ([PASPI Monitor, 2022](#); PASPI, 2023^{a,b,c}). Business actors (operators/traders) are given an 18-month grace period for compliance, where all operators/traders are required to comply with these regulations by 29 December 2024. Meanwhile, Smallholder Enterprises (SMEs) are given a transition period with a longer period of 24 months or SMEs are required to comply with these regulations starting 29 June 2025.

The EUDR policy contains the following provisions: (1) prohibiting the marketing of commodities/products associated with deforestation along the supply chain in the EU region. The commodities referred to are soybeans, livestock, palm oil, wood, cocoa, coffee, and rubber (including their respective derivative products); (2) requiring the submission of supply chain information (traceability) including geolocation, (3) mandatory due diligence for risk assessment and risk mitigation; and (4) deforestation-free certification following the EU standards issued by the EU authorities.

By applying the EUDR only to the above commodities, the EU implicitly views that deforestation only occurs in countries producing these commodities. However, deforestation is a normal phenomenon of the development process that has occurred in almost all countries in the world since the beginning of civilization until now, including in mainland Europe (Matthew, 1983; Walker, 1993; Houghton, 1996; Bhattarai *et al.*, 2001; FAO, 2012; USDA, 2014; Keenan *et al.*, 2015; Kaplan *et al.*, 2017; Sabatini *et al.*, 2018; Barredo *et al.*, 2021; PASPI, 2023 [PASPI, 2023](#)). Therefore, if the question is about deforestation, the EUDR should be applied to all commodities/products produced in all countries.

The discriminatory enforcement of the EUDR contradicts international agreements within the WTO, namely relating to the principles of non-discrimination, fair trade, and efficient trade. In this regard, the WTO is an international organization that regulates international trade which was formed on 5 April 1994 in Marrakesh (Morocco) and began implementing international trade principles on 1 January 1995. The EU and Indonesia are members of the WTO, so the EU trade policies should follow WTO trade guidelines and principles.

Apart from violating the WTO trade principles, the EU should also respect the internationally agreed-upon mechanism, namely notifying the EUDR to the WTO first. Only if the world community agrees with this trade policy, can the EUDR then be implemented internationally. The ways in which the EU imposes its regulations on other countries unilaterally, which Bardford (2020) calls the "Brussel Effect", is a neo-imperialist practice that has long been abandoned by the global community.

POTENTIAL VIOLATIONS OF WTO NON-DISCRIMINATION PRINCIPLES

There are at least four aspects in the EUDR that have the potential to violate WTO principles. **First**, the principle of non-discrimination in trade between countries (Most Favored Nation/MFN). Each member country is prohibited from implementing policies that discriminate against like goods and services (like products, direct competitors, substitutable products) imported by a country from various countries (Article I GATT 1994 and Article II GATS).

In this context, palm oil is one of 17 types of vegetable oil traded internationally and is among the vegetable oils imported by the EU from other countries. The EU annually imports vegetable oils such as palm oil, soybean oil, rapeseed oil, sunflower oil, peanut oil, and others (Oil World, 2022). All these vegetable oils are categorized by FAO as food and oil/fat substances with the same/similar functions, namely as a source of energy and fatty acids. In the global consumption of vegetable oils,

as food, energy and oleochemicals, there is mutual substitution and competition between vegetable oils (Morgan, 1993; Kojima *et al.*, 2016, Santeramo, 2017; Parcell, 2018; Shigetomi *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, in the context of the WTO non-discrimination principle, all vegetable oils are considered “like products”, “direct competitors”, and “substitutable products”.

In this context, the EUDR only applies to palm oil and soybean oil. This policy does not apply to rapeseed oil and sunflower oil (as well as 10 other types of vegetable oils) which the EU also imports from other countries. This can clearly be categorized as violating the principle of non-discrimination between MFN countries.

Second, the principle of non-discrimination of like goods and services between imported and domestic production (National Treatment/NT) both de jure and de facto (Article III GATT 1994 and Article XVIII GATS). Domestic vegetable oils produced domestically by the European Union include rapeseed oil, sunflower oil, cottonseed oil, and olive oil ([USDA, 2023](#)). EU-produced vegetable oils are also “like products”, “direct competitors”, and “substitutable products” for the palm oil imported by the EU.

In this context, the EUDR also practices discrimination (National Treatment) by applying the EUDR only to imported palm oil and soybean oil, but not to domestically produced EU vegetable oils such as rapeseed oil, sunflower oil, cottonseed oil, and olive oil.

Third, Non-Tariff Barriers contained in Article II and Article IX of GATT 1994. According to UNCTAD (2010), the Non-Tariff Measure (NTM) policy is a non-tariff policy that has the potential to have an economic impact on international trade, altering the traded quantity, or price, or both. According to this principle, member countries are not allowed to create policies on all forms of non-tariff barriers in the form of quotas, restrictions, procedures (red tape) or certain conditions to limit the entry of imported goods with the aim of protecting domestic industries/commodities.

The EUDR policy can be categorized as a Non-Tariff Barrier in international trade. The deforestation-free requirement and all the verification mechanisms along the supply chain not only hinder palm oil trade to the EU but also have the potential to stop palm oil trade to the EU.

Apart from being a non-tariff barrier, deforestation-free is also a form of non-price competition ([PASPI, 2023](#)) to protect EU vegetable oils (especially rapeseed oil). Even though it has been subsidized by the EU government, rapeseed oil cannot compete with palm oil.

Fourth, the principle of Technical Barrier to Trade (TBT). Several GATT provisions covering the TBT issue include article I, article III, article IX, article X, article XI, and article XX. TBT or technical barriers in trade are barriers caused by technical aspects such as product quality, packaging, labelling, and safety requirements.

This principle includes Technical Regulations, Technical Standards, and Conformity Assessment Procedures, but remains under the principles of non-discrimination, transparency, and harmonization. Each member has the right to implement technical arrangements and standardization of a product, including testing procedures for compliance with standards determined by the principles of non-discrimination (domestic versus imported products), transparency (announced to the global public and notified to the WTO), and as far as possible in harmony with global standards (harmonization).

Based on these WTO principles, the EU may apply the technical requirements and testing procedures contained in the EUDR set of rules. However, technical requirements, procedures and other forms of TBT must be applied to all “like products”, “direct competitors”, and “substitutable products” commodities. Even if deforestation-free becomes a form of TBT, the EUDR must be applied to all commodities/products worldwide, including all commodities/products produced within the EU region.

CONCLUSION

The EUDR policy prohibits palm oil and its derivative products (as well as six other commodities and their respective derivative products) that are linked to deforestation from entering the European Union market. This policy applies to imported commodities/products or those produced by other countries outside the EU region. This indicates that the EU implicitly views deforestation as only occurring in countries producing these commodities. In fact, deforestation is a normal phenomenon of the development process that has occurred in almost all countries worldwide since the beginning of civilization until now, including in mainland Europe.

The discriminatory application of the EUDR contradicts international agreements contained in the WTO, namely relating to the principles of non-discrimination and fair trade. The four WTO non-discrimination principles that EUDR has the potential to violate are: (1) the principle of non-discrimination in trade between countries (Most Favored Nation/MFN); (2) the principle of non-discrimination of imported like goods compared to domestic production (National Treatment/NT); (3) non-tariff trade barriers; and (4) the discriminatory Technical Barrier to Trade (TBT) principle.

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